

THE RESPONSE OF STEEL-BASED FIBRE-METAL LAMINATES TO LOCALISED BLAST LOADING

G.S. Langdon and L.A. Rowe
Blast Impact and Survivability Research Unit, University of Cape Town,
Rondebosch 7700, South Africa.
genevieve.langdon@uct.ac.za

ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the results of blast tests on plain glass-fibre reinforced polypropylene panels and fibre-metal laminate (FML) panels comprising steel sheets and layers of glass-fibre reinforced polypropylene. The blast-loaded composite panels exhibited fibre fracture and pull through modes of failure. The adhesion at the steel-composite interface in the FMLs was investigated using three point bending and it was shown that a single heating/pressing operation had better performance than the two-stage methods and those involving a third party adhesive. The blast loaded FML panels exhibited large inelastic deformation and debonding failure of the steel-composite interfaces. These were similar to those exhibited by blast loaded FMLs manufactured with the same composite material but with aluminium alloy sheets. Non-dimensional analysis of the FML panels showed that non-dimensional displacements were lower than the equivalent aluminium based FMLs, but were approximately 20 % higher than monolithic steel.

Keywords: fibre-metal laminate, blast loading, debonding failure, panel, twintex

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-metal laminates (FMLs) are hybrid structural materials comprising interleaved metal sheets and fibre-reinforced polymers. Glass fibre (GF) reinforced polymers are used on cost and performance grounds, while aluminium is the most common choice for the FML metal. The most commonly used FML is GLARE[®] which comprises thin sheets of aluminium alloy and glass fibre reinforced epoxy. GLARE[®] is widely used by the aerospace industry due to its excellent fatigue and impact properties, relative to monolithic aluminium alloy [1-2]. Recent experiments examining the blast resistance of GLARE[®] panels were reported by Langdon et al [3].

While aluminium alloy and epoxy resins are the most popular choices for FML construction, other options have been considered by researchers. Langdon *et al* [4-6] performed blast tests on aluminium alloy-glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (GFPP) FMLs. Some advantages of using polypropylene include the higher fracture toughness, good recyclability and reparability of the thermoplastic polymer. Recent modelling work by Karagiozova et al [7] showed that blast loaded FML panels are able to distribute the loading more evenly across the panel than some sandwich and monolithic metal configurations, thus offering potential advantages in a blast containment situation. One of the drawbacks of the FMLs tested by Langdon et al [4-6] was the relatively high

cost of the aluminium alloy. FMLs with magnesium and titanium sheets are in the development stages [8-9] and Van Rooijen *et al* [10] have attempted to develop stainless steel-GF epoxy FMLs. Van Rooijen *et al* [10] studied the bonding at the steel-composite interface, but concluded that acceptable levels of bond strength were not attained [10]. This work examines the use of steel in FML construction, as it is significantly cheaper than aluminium alloy and may be suitable for applications where weight is not a critical issue. This paper examines the blast performance of plain GFPP composites and steel-GFPP based FML panels.

MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

The FML panels for the blast tests were manufactured from 0.4 mm thick steel sheets, co-mingled GFPP woven cloth and a polypropylene interlayer. In order to promote better adhesion, the steel sheets were abraded using silicon grit paper and cleaned with acetone. The various layers were stacked in a mould, heated to the processing temperature of the composite (185°C) and cold stamped at a constant pressure (1300 kPa). This ensured a rapid rate of cooling and a low degree of crystallinity within the matrix [11]. All panels had the warp and weft fibres aligned parallel to the panel edges. Three stacking configurations were investigated by varying the number of steel sheets from 2 to 4 and keeping the number of plies (8 plies) constant between each pair of steel sheets. Some additional panels containing GFPP only were also manufactured to ascertain the influence of adding the steel sheets to the composite. The FML panels are identified using SXTY nomenclature, where S = steel, X = number of steel sheets, T = GFPP and Y = number of blocks of GFPP. Similar nomenclature was used in references [4-6].

Bonding Investigation

The effectiveness of the bonding along the steel-GFPP interface was investigated by first manufacturing FML panels using six different bonding options. The panels were manufactured with two sheets of steel and one block of GFPP containing 8 plies. The same GFPP composite used in the blast tests was used in the bonding investigation but thicker steel sheets were employed in the bonding investigation (0.9 mm thick mild steel rather than 0.4 mm thick steel sheets). The six bonding options investigated were:

- Single cycle FMLs: these were manufactured as described above.
- Two stage manufacture (PP interlayer): the GFPP layer was first heated and pressed as described above, then stacked with the steel and a PP interlayer. The re-stacked FMLs were then re-heated to 185°C and cold-pressed.
- Two stage manufacture (PEVA interlayer): the GFPP layer was first heated and pressed, then stacked with the steel and a polyethylene vinyl acetate (PEVA) interlayer film. The re-stacked FMLs were then heated to the processing temperature of the PEVA film (105 °C) and cold-pressed.
- Vinyl Ester (3rd party adhesive): the GFPP layer was heated and pressed as described, then stacked with the steel and bonded using vinyl ester resin.

- SP 4202 epoxy resin (3rd party adhesive): the GFPP layer was heated and pressed, then stacked with the steel and bonded using SP 4202 epoxy resin. In order to cure the epoxy resin, the stack was heated for 40 minutes at 120 °C.
- Methyl methacrylate (3rd party adhesive): the GFPP layer was first heated and pressed, then stacked with the steel and bonded (room temperature cured) using a commercially available, general purpose, methyl methacrylate adhesive.

Given the large mismatch in elastic moduli between the steel and GFPP layers, it was anticipated that flexural testing would reveal the difference in bond strength between the six manufacturing processes. Three point bend tests were performed upon samples machined from the six FML panels. ASTM standard D5023-01 was followed. All tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. A graph displaying typical force versus displacement curves obtained from the three point bend tests is shown in Figure 1. Photographs of typical failed specimens are shown in Figure 2. It is evident from Figure 1 that the panels manufactured in a single cycle failed at a higher peak force and were able to absorb significantly more energy than any of their counterparts. The PP film two stage process manufactured specimens initially exhibited a similar curve to the single-stacking process but exhibited a lower residual energy absorbing capacity. The two stage process with PP interlayer was better than PEVA film 2 stage method and the third party adhesive methods. The third party adhesive methods were all poor performers and exhibited a similar debonding failure within the adhesive. The epoxy resin bond was significantly stronger than the vinyl ester and methyl methacrylate bonds, exhibiting three times the peak force at failure but showed similar residual properties.

Figure 1: Graph showing the force-displacement curves obtained from three point bending tests on the FML panels manufactured using different processes

It was encouraging that the single cycle process showed superior performance as it was also the cheapest manufacturing method (fewest processing steps) and retained the advantages of using a thermoplastic composite by not introducing a third party (thermosetting) resin. As a result of the flexural test results, the FML panels for the blast tests were all manufactured using the single cycle process.

Figure 2: Photographs of typical failed specimens arising from the three point bend tests

CHARACTERISATION OF THE BLAST LOADED PANEL MATERIALS

Microhardness testing of the 0.4 mm thick steel sheets

Microhardness testing of the 0.4 mm thick steel sheet was performed according to ASTM Standard E92-82 (2003) at a load of 20 kgf (196 N). The hardness numbers were converted into ultimate tensile strength (UTS) estimates. 50 % of the sheets had a UTS in the range 335 to 340 MPa, whereas the other 50% of the steel sheets had a UTS in the range 360 to 370 MPa. The sheets were grouped together; the sheets with the lower UTS values were used to manufacture the FMLs with two steel sheets, whereas the sheets with the higher UTS (360 to 370 MPa) were used to manufacture FMLs with three and four steel sheets.

Flexural Testing

Three point bend tests were performed, using ASTM standard D5023, on 30 ± 1 mm wide rectangular pieces cut from the FML and GFPP panels to be blasted. The strain rate was kept constant at $3.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ by varying the cross-head speed (between 1.76 and 5.73 mm/min) and adjusting the span of the specimen to maintain a constant span to thickness ratio of 16:1. The results are given in Table 1. It is observed that the

experimentally obtained flexural moduli for the GFPP specimens were 20% lower than the manufacturers value of 13 GPa [12]. The flexural modulus of the FML panels decreased as panel thickness increased, due to the higher proportion of composite in the cross-section.

Table 1: Summary of Results from Three-Point Bend Tests (mean average values)

<i>GFPP Specimens</i>				
Specimen Type	No. of plies	Thickness (mm)	Experimental (EI) (Nm ²)	Experimental E (GPa)
T8	8	4.16	1.9	10.5
T16	16	7.88	14.8	11.3
T24	24	11.62	45.1	11.4
<i>FML Specimens</i>				
Specimen Type	Thickness (mm)	Experimental (EI) (Nm ²)	Calculated (experimental) E, averaged over section (GPa)	
S2T18	4.87	12.7	43.8	
S3T28	9.13	69.9	37.4	
S4T38	13.50	213.8	33.3	

BLAST EXPERIMENTS

All the panels were clamped between two frames, giving a square exposed area with a side length of 200 mm. The frames were mounted to a ballistic pendulum; the impulse is calculated from the pendulum swing. Localised blast loading was generated by detonating 30 mm diameter discs of PE4 plastic explosive, at a stand-off distance of 13 mm, located centrally on the panel. A photograph of the experimental configuration is shown in Figure 3. Several panels of each configuration were tested using different masses of PE4 to vary the impulse.

Figure 3: Photograph of experimental arrangement (viewed from above)

BLAST TEST RESULTS

The GFPP panels exhibited various failure modes, including matrix cracking, fibre fracture and fibre pull through, with damage increasing at higher impulses. Examples of these failure modes are shown in Figure 4. The blast tests results are given in Table 2. The FML panels exhibited similar failure modes to those previously observed in aluminium-GFPP panels subjected to localised blast loading [4-6], namely:

- Pitting of the front face exposed to the blast, shown in Figure 5a,
- Ring-buckling, a particular debonding pattern found in the front face exposed to the blast, shown in Figure 5b,
- Multiple debonding failures of the steel-composite interface, shown in Figure 5c and Figure 6 for the internal layers and Figure 5d and Figure 6 for the front and back facesheets,
- large plastic deformation of the metal layers as shown in Figure 6,
- petalling failure of the back steel sheet at higher impulses, and
- Fibre fracture, shown in Figure 6.

(a) Initial fibre damage

(b) Fibre fracture and pull-through

Figure 4: Photographs of GFPP panels, showing various failure modes

(a) Pitting of the front face

(b) Ring buckling of the front face

(c) Internal debonding

(d) Front and back face debonding

Figure 5: Photographs of selected FML panels showing various failure modes

Figure 6: Photographs of two cross-sections from blast loaded FML panels

Table 2: Results from the blast tests

Panel Designation	Total thickness (mm)	Impulse (Ns)	Back face mid-point displacement (mm)	Failure Modes
GFPP composite panels				
T1-4	4.16	3.2	0.30	MC, FF(initiation)
T1-1	4.00	6.4	-	MC, FF
T1-2	4.12	8.5	-	MC, FF
T2-2	7.70	6.0	1.76	MC, FF(initiation)
T2-3	7.52	10.2	3.80	MC, FF
T2-4	8.08	10.5	-	MC, FF
T3-5	11.00	4.8	0.93	MC, FF(initiation)
T3-4	11.16	7.6	2.62	MC, FF
T3-3	11.17	11.5	2.72	MC, FF
T3-1	12.38	10.8	-	MC, FF
T3-2	11.12	17.0	-	MC, FF
FML panels				
S2T1-5	4.98	3.2	8.99	I: P, DB, PD
S2T1-2	4.93	5.7	14.72	I: P, DB, PD
S2T1-1	4.86	9.6	19.09	I: P, DB, PD, FF
S2T1-4	4.92	11.4	-	II: P, DB, PD, FF
S2T1-6	4.87	13.2	-	II: P, DB, PD, FF, PET
S3T2-1	9.00	9.0	17.12	I: P, DB, PD
S3T2-2	9.15	12.2	23.09	I: P, DB, PD
S3T2-4	8.99	13.2	23.28	I: P, DB, PD, FF(minor)
S3T2-3	8.98	17.1	-	II: P, DB, PD, FF
S3T2-5	9.07	18.0	-	II: P, DB, PD, FF, PET
S4T3-3	12.64	12.2	20.33	I: P, DB, PD
S4T3-2	13.49	18.6	22.74	I: P, DB, PD
S4T3-1	13.52	22.3	28.65	I: P, DB, PD, FF
S4T3-4	13.04	25.8	-	II: P, DB, PD, FF, PET

¹DB - debonding; P - pitting; RB - ring buckling; PD or I - plastic deformation; MC - matrix cracking; FF - fibre fracture; II - tearing of the back face; PET - petalling

A graph of back face displacement versus impulse is shown in Figure 7. In all cases back face displacement increased with increasing impulse, as expected. The GFPP panels exhibited little permanent displacement (less than 5 mm) prior to failure by rupture and fibre breakage; this was also expected given that the material is known to be elastic up to failure. The FML panels exhibited larger permanent displacements of the back face, mainly due to the debonding of the rear steel sheet. The inner composite layers rebounded elastically and exhibited small permanent displacements, as shown in the cross-section photograph in Figure 6a. The elastic rebound of the composite layer is the cause of the buckling evident in the inner steel layers of the S3T2 and S4T3 panels (that is, the rippling of the internal steel sheet shown in Figures 5c and 6a). The displacements of the FML panels increase linearly with increasing impulse for a given FML configuration. Surprisingly, increasing the number of steel layers from two to three produced only a small difference in the back face displacements for a given impulse prior to rupture. The S3T2 FMLs have a higher back face tearing threshold impulse, meaning that there is an advantage to the thicker FML construction. The S4T3 panels showed the lowest displacements for a given impulse and also had the highest back face tearing threshold. However, it should be noted that the S4T3 FMLs are considerably thicker and heavier than the other configurations.

Figure 7: Graph of back face displacement versus impulse for the blast tested panels

The experimental results were non-dimensionalised following the same approach as Lemanski et al [5]. The back face displacement is normalised against panel thickness and the impulse is normalised using a non-dimensional impulse parameter given in Eq. (1). The density and UTS of the FML panels were calculated as an average across the section [5]. The non-dimensional displacement versus non-dimensional impulse graph is shown in Figure 8. All of the data from the FML tests appears to sit on a linear trend-

line, with non-dimensional displacements that are lower than those obtained for FMLs with aluminium alloy sheets [5] but are approximately 20 % higher than those for steel panels [13]. The data from the GFPP only panels follows a separate trend with much lower permanent displacements, due to the large elastic recovery of the composite.

$$\phi_{qt} = \frac{I(1 + \ln\left(\frac{BL}{\pi R_0^2}\right))}{2t^2 \sqrt{BL\rho_f \sigma_0}} \quad (1)$$

Where B = breadth, I = impulse, L = length, R_0 = load radius, t = thickness, ρ_f = density and σ_0 = characteristic stress (in this case the smeared UTS).

Figure 8: Graph of non-dimensional back face displacement versus non-dimensional impulse (excluding torn panels)

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

Results from blast tests on steel based FML panels with two, three and four sheets of steel show that the panels exhibited similar failure modes to those previously reported for FML panels manufactured with aluminium alloy sheets [4-6]. The main failure modes were large plastic deformation of the steel and debonding of the steel-composite interfaces (debonding of the back face, ring buckling on the front face). The steel FML panels exhibited normalised back face displacements that were lower than aluminium based FMLs [5] but were approximately 20 % higher than those found for monolithic steel plates [13].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are indebted to the University Research Committee, University of Cape Town for financial support. The authors also wish to thank Mr R. Smit (CSIR) for his assistance with the blast tests, Dr CJ von Klemperer for his technical advice throughout the project and Prof GN Nurick for his helpful comments during the preparation of this paper.

References

1. A. Vlot, Impact loading on fibre metal laminates. *Int J Impact Eng* **18(3)**, pp. 291-307, 1996.
2. L.B. Vogelesang, A. Vlot, Development of fibre metal laminates for advanced aerospace structures, *J Materials Proc Tech* **103**, pp. 1-5, 2000.
3. G.S. Langdon, Y. Chi, G.N. Nurick, P. Haupt. Response of GLARE© panels to blast loading, *Eng Structures* (in review).
4. G.S. Langdon, S.L. Lemanski, G.N. Nurick, M.C. Simmons, W.J. Cantwell and G.K. Schleyer. Behaviour of fibre-metal laminates subjected to localised blast loading: Part I – experimental observations and failure analysis, *Int. J. Impact Eng*, **34(7)**, pp. 1202-1222, 2007.
5. S.L. Lemanski, G.N. Nurick, G.S. Langdon, M.C. Simmons, W.J. Cantwell and G.K. Schleyer. Behaviour of fibre-metal laminates subjected to localised blast loading: Part II – quantitative analysis, *Int. J. Impact Eng*, **34(7)**, pp. 1223-1245, 2007.
6. G.S. Langdon, G.N. Nurick, S.L. Lemanski, M.C. Simmons, W.J. Cantwell, G.K. Schleyer, Failure characterisation of blast-loaded fibre-metal laminate panels based on aluminium and glass-fibre reinforced polypropylene, *Compos Sci Tech* **67(7-8)** pp. 1385-1405, 2007.
7. D. Karagiozova, G.S. Langdon, G.N. Nurick, S. Chung Kim Yuen. Simulation of the response of fibre-metal laminates to localised blast loading, *Int. J. Impact Eng* (in press). doi: 10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2009.04.001
8. P. Cortes, W.J. Cantwell, The fracture properties of a fibre-metal laminate based on magnesium alloy, *Compos Pt B*, **37** pp. 163-170, 2006.
9. P. Cortes, W.J. Cantwell, The prediction of failure in titanium-based thermoplastic fibre-metal laminates, *Compos Sci Tech*, **66**, pp. 2306-2316, 2006.
10. R.G.J. Van Rooijen, J. Sinke, S. Van Der Zwaag, Improving the adhesion of thin stainless steel sheets for fibre metal laminate (FML) applications, *J Adhesion Sci Technol*, **19(16)**, pp. 1387–1396, 2005.
11. F. Guillen, W.J. Cantwell, The influence of cooling rate on the fracture properties of a thermoplastic-based fibre metal laminate, *J. Reinforced Plastics and Comp.*, **21**, pp. 749-772, 2002.
12. Saint-Gobain Vetrotex (website), www.twintex.com, 2004.
13. N. Jacob, G.N. Nurick, G.S. Langdon, The effect of stand-off distance on the failure of fully clamped circular mild steel plates subjected to blast loads, *Eng Structures*, **29**, pp. 2723-2736, 2007.